

SEVEN YEARS OLD GIRL WITH DUCTAL CARCINOMA IN SITU – A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Background Breast cancer in very young women is sporadic, usually have more aggressive biological characteristics, present at a later stage and is associated with a poor prognosis. It is hard to diagnosis and often late to be diagnosed. We reported a case of breast cancer in 7 years old girl who was accidentally found in operation expected to be a benign lesion. **Case Summary** A female, Asian, 7-years-old complaining of a mass and enlargement in her left breast since one year prior came to the hospital. No family history of breast or ovarian cancer in primary relatives. Previous excisional biopsy in a rural hospital six months earlier revealed a 3.2 cm ductal carcinoma in situ (DIN2) with differential diagnosis of papillary ductal carcinoma. Estrogen, progesterone and Her2 receptors were negatives. Physical examination found enlargement of the left breast, unclear tumour boundaries, Ultrasound demonstrated a 4-cm mass in her upper lateral of the left breast (ACR BI-RADS 5 - highly suspicious of malignancy), while no findings in her right breast. No findings on chest X-ray and abdominal ultrasound. The patient was diagnosed with ductal carcinoma in situ of the left breast, cTisN0M0, Stage 0, Karnofsky 80%. She was offered modified radical mastectomy, no chemotherapy and neither radiation therapy performed. Routine follow-up every three months was done. There were no findings on physical, chest X-ray, and abdominal ultrasound, CEA& Ca 15-3 level were average. Two years follow up remains free of recurrence. **Conclusion** Sufficient resection margins need for treatment of breast cancer in young women because it has a higher rate of local recurrence. Adjuvant treatment options may different compared with older women; there need judgment and tailoring of the treatment.

KEYWORDS breast cancer, young women, carcinoma in situ

INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer in very young women is a complicated disease. It is very rare, the incidence of 20-24 years: 1.4 / 100.000 women

and < 20 years are 0.1 / 100,000 women [1,2]. Usually have more aggressive biological characteristics, present at a later stage, high risk of local recurrence, correlated with contralateral breast cancer and is associated with an inferior prognosis [3-5]. Breast Cancer in Young Women was associated cancer syndromes; Hereditary Breast and Ovarian Cancer (BRCA 1/2), Li-Fraumeni (TP53), Cowden (PTEN), Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer (CDH1, Peutz-Jeghers (STK11) [6,7]. Ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS) is a noninvasive mammary carcinoma; the lactiferous duct cell membrane turns into a cancer cell, but has not invaded the duct wall and surrounding breast tissue [8,9]. One in five cases of early-stage mammary carcinoma suffers from DCIS. The American Cancer Society estimates that the number of new cases of Carcinoma mammary in the United States in 2016 is 246,660 people, about 61,000 new cases are in situ carcinoma [10].

The purpose of this paper is to report a case of breast cancer

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in a young woman who estimated a benign lesion, difficulty in diagnosis and discussion among tumour board members in the choosing the treatment.

CASE REPORT

We report the case of a female, Asian, 7-years-old, complaining of a mass and enlargement in her left breast since one year prior came to the hospital. There was no family history of breast or ovarian cancer in a primary relative. Excisional biopsy was done in Enrekang General Hospital (a rural hospital about 265 km from the capital city of Makassar), revealed a 3.2 cm ductal carcinoma in situ.

Histopathology Results from previous excisional biopsy as shown in figure 1 and 2: tissue show ductal proliferation and mammary gland acini. In the ducts, the ductal epithelial epithelium appears to be proliferation forming a clear papillary structure with fibrovascular stalk with epithelial-looking atrial epithelial cells, with low to moderate grade atypia. Overall the basal membrane is generally intact, myoepithelial apparent. Conclusion: Ductal carcinoma in situ. Differential diagnosis; papillary ductal carcinoma in situ (Tavassoli classification DIN 2). When the patient came to Hasanuddin University Hospital,

Figure 1: Excisional biopsy specimens.

Figure 2: Microscopic Excisional biopsy.

performed breast ultrasound demonstrated a 4-cm mass with associated microcalcifications in her left breast (ACR BIRADS 5), while no findings in her right breast. No findings on chest X-ray and abdominal ultrasound. CA 15-3 : 6.12 U/ml (normal:13-40.0); CEA 1.64 ng/mL (normal 0 – 4.70). Estrogen, progesterone and Her2 receptors were negatives. The patient was diagnosed

Figure 3: Preoperative.

Figure 4: Operation.

Figure 5: Specimen.

Figure 6: Specimens Post Operative.

Hasil Histopatologi

Figure 7: A specimen of Lymph node.

with ductal carcinoma in situ of the left breast, cTisN0M0, Stage 0, Karnofsky 80%. She was offered modified radical mastectomy as shown in figure 3, 4 and 5. Enlargement of one axillary lymph nodes was found.

Postoperative histopathology results; cystic-appearing mammary glands, in some focus, appearing to be a proliferation of acinus cells and mammary glandular ductal, with small, atypical nuclei, monomorphic with the intact basal membrane, between the connective tissue stroma as shown in figure 6. The lymph node preparations show some lymphoid follicles with a visible germinal centre, at the other focal points of dilated sinuses containing histiocytes as shown in figure 7. Conclusions: Atypical Ductal Hyperplasia, Sinus Histiocytosis

Postoperatively, we did not offer chemotherapy and neither radiation therapy. Routine follow-up every three months was done. There were no findings on physical, chest X-ray, and abdominal ultrasound, CEA & Ca 15-3 level were average, presently remains free of recurrence. Timeline of the case shown in table 1.

DISCUSSION

Breast cancer is harder to diagnose in young women [11]. In this case with incisional biopsy results: ductal carcinoma in situ (DIN2), differential diagnosis of papillary ductal carcinoma in situ, we need to performed several meeting with our tumour board to ensure whether this case is precancer/cancer. Results of discussions with the pathologist's section obtained confirmation that this patient is ductal carcinoma in situ. Immunohistochemistry found Estrogen, progesterone and HER2 receptors were negative. This is in other studies which found a higher prevalence of high grade, ER-negative, HER2-positive, and basal-like carcinomas in young women with breast cancer [3,7]. Routine blood examination is within normal limits indicating the cancer is still in its early stages which have not an anaemia effect. Chemical analysis of blood within normal limits signifies not yet metastasises to the bone marrow and liver. Tumour markers (CA 15-3 and CEA) within the normal range. Ca 15-3 be epitopes of a transmembrane glycoprotein called MUC1, located on chromosome 1q21-24 with a glycoprotein code of 160 kDa and 230 bp [12] MUC1 muscle is found on the luminal surface of the normal glandular epithelium. MUC1 is upregulated and secreted by large numbers by cancer cells, causing the MUC1 expression to be detected far from the primary cell and circulating in the circulation [12]. CA 15-3 has a low sensitivity and specificity in the early stages of disease and increases as the disease progresses, with a sensitivity of 10% in stage I patients, 20% in stage II, 40% in stage III and 75% in stage IV [13]. CEA is a marker of the human developmental tumour and contains cloning of CD66e cluster differentiation [14]. CEA increased markedly only in the moderate and advanced stages. CEA examination for therapeutic response and prognosis determination. If high levels of preoperative CEA generally have metastasis and invasion of the vascular or lymphatic system, it is found in 40-50% of metastatic cancer patients [12,15].

Therapy options also became our concerned. In these patients there is a discrepancy between the biopsy results of carcinoma in situ, with relatively large tumour size, then the decision to perform the surgery becomes difficult. Because the goal of the operation is curative, the procedure for curative in breast cancer is breast conserving surgery or modified radical mastectomy. We did not offer breast-conserving surgery, because a biopsy has been previously done in the rural hospital and it is not clear of tumour boundaries, also a small proportion of the tumour size and breasts. Studies found that age is a definite factor of local recurrence in younger patients, having higher failure rates after limited surgery and radiation [16,17]. Various studies of breast cancer at a young age associated with high local recurrence, more aggressive local therapy is needed [16,17]. Thus, we performed a modified radical mastectomy.

We did not offer chemotherapy and radiation therapy as adjuvant therapy because it was early breast cancer and considering the patient is still in the development phase. In this patient watchful waiting is done with a close follow-up.

There are two similar cases: Ontario-Canada-2008: Ms AH, four years old, 2 cm breast mass, diagnosis: secretory breast cancer, management: a double mastectomy, no chemo nor radiation. Utah USA- 2013: Ms CT, eight years old, history of mother- cervix cancer and father- Non-Hodgkin lymphoma, 2 cm breast mass, diagnosis secretory breast cancer, treatment: a double mastectomy, no chemotherapy nor radiation.

Table 1 Timeline of the Case.

Dates	Relevant Past Medical History and Interventions		
20/03/2015	The patient came to Enrekang Hospital (a rural hospital about 265 KM from the capital province of Makassar) complaining of a mass and enlargement in her left breast since one year prior came to the hospital. There was no family history of breast or ovarian cancer in a primary relative.		
28/03/2015	The Surgeon estimated a benign lesion. Excisional biopsy was done in the hospital. Pathological results revealed a 3.2 cm ductal carcinoma in situ.		
18/09/2015	The patient referred to Hasanuddin University hospital in Makassar due to the pathological result of ductal carcinoma in situ.		
Dates	Summaries from Initial and Follow-up Visits	Diagnostic Testing	Interventions
20/09/2015	Patient's came to Hasanuddin University Hospital, a top referral hospital in Makassar. Physical Examination: Enlargement of the left breast. It is not clear of tumour boundaries.	20/09/2015 Breast USG: Mass in the upper lateral of the left breast. 20/09/2015 Abdominal USG: no metastases 20/09/2015 Chest X-rays: no metastases 21/09/2015 CA 15-3 : 6.12 (normal :13-40 U/ml) 21/09/2015 CEA 1.64 ng/mL (normal 0 – 4.70) 24/09/2015 Immunohistochemistry: ER -, PR -, Her2 -	Modified Radical Mastectomy Wound care Genetic counselling
10/03/2016	Follow-up visits: No complaints, physical examination on loco-regional: no tumour mass found.	There were no findings on physical, chest X-ray, and abdominal ultrasound.	Genetic counselling. Education
20/02/2017	Follow-up visits: No complaints, physical examination on loco-regional: no tumour mass found.	There were no findings on physical, chest X-ray, and abdominal ultrasound. CA 15-3 : 7.22 U/ml (normal :13-40,0) ; CEA 1.87 ng/mL (normal 0 – 4.70)	Genetic counselling. Education
10/05/2018	Follow-up visits: No complaints, physical examination on loco-regional: no tumour mass found.	There were no findings on physical, chest X-ray, and abdominal ultrasound.	Genetic counselling. Education

CONCLUSION

Diagnosis breast cancer in very young women is difficult. Sufficient resection margins need for treatment of breast cancer in young women because it has a higher rate of local recurrence. Adjuvant treatment options may different compared with older women; there need tailoring of the treatment.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

The participation of each author corresponds to the criteria of authorship and contributorship emphasised in the Recommendations for the Conduct, Reporting, Editing, and Publication of Scholarly work in Medical Journals of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors. Indeed, all the authors have actively participated in the redaction, the revision of the manuscript and provided approval for this final revised version.

PATIENT CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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